

Studies in the Xanthone Group.

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γ -Pyrone ring is known to possess fairly developed chromogenetic properties. Though some of the hydroxyxanthonones (*viz.*, gentisin and euxanthone) have been used for dyeing purposes, they are all feeble dyestuffs of yellow shades only. No attempt appears to have been made to introduce groups, specially those having chromophoric nuclei, in xanthone molecule and thereby obtain derivatives which would in all probability possess more interesting and well developed tinctorial properties and, therefore, better adapted for dyeing purpose. Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 749) described the preparation of a few (three only) azo derivatives from nitroamino xanthone, but their tinctorial properties were not studied.

The present investigation was undertaken mainly with the object of preparing such derivatives of xanthone as are expected to be useful for dyeing purpose.

Of the various possible simple monoamino derivatives of xanthone 3-aminoxanthone, being the only one which is definitely known, was mostly utilised as the starting material.

A number of azo compounds have been prepared by coupling diazotised 3-aminoxanthone with various phenols and amines such as, phenol, resorcinol, salicylic acid, β -naphthol, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, G-acid, R-acid and dimethylaniline. Most of these azo derivatives resist all attempts to crystallisation (*cf.* Dhar, *loc. cit.*). They dye wool from 1% sulphuric acid bath and silk from acetic acid bath in shades varying from yellow to light pink.

It was expected that the acylaminoxanthonones, *e.g.*, 3-benzoylaminoxanthone, 2-nitro-7-benzoylaminoxanthone and oxaldi-3-xanthonylamide would give vat dyes like the acylaminoanthraquinones (*cf.* D. Z. 16772; F. P. 400653, etc.) and acylaminophenanthraquinones (*cf.* Mukherjee and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 619) but the benzoylaminoxanthonones were found to be almost colourless and the oxal derivative, though coloured, could not be made to yield a soluble vat.

The azomethine group, like the azo-linking, is known to enhance tinctorial properties (*cf.* Green and Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2242; Morgan and Reeves, *ibid*, 1922, 121, 1; Sircar and Sen-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 321).

An azomethine group was introduced into the xanthone molecule by the condensation of 3-aminoxanthone with various aromatic aldehydes (*vide* experimental) and it has been found that the xanthone

phenylazomethines, though coloured, are not at all suitable for dyeing purposes. They are very unstable easily hydrolysing even by boiling water.

Two new derivatives of xanthone, namely 3-iodoxanthone and 2-nitro-7-iodoxanthone have been prepared from the corresponding amino compounds *via* diazo reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Xanthone-3-azo-phenol.

A solution of 3-aminoxanthone (1 mol.) in hydrochloric acid (2½ mols.) was cooled to 0° and diazotised in the usual way with sodium nitrite (1 mol.). When the diazotisation was complete the mixture was treated with one molecule of phenol dissolved in excess of caustic soda. After two hours the reaction product was separated as a red precipitate by acidification. It crystallised from pyridine as deep orange-red small rhombic plates, not melting below 300°. It dissolves in acetic acid or sulphuric acid with a red colour. It is not satisfactorily absorbed either by wool or silk. (Found: N, 9.3. $C_{19}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.8 per cent). The other azo compounds prepared are described in Table I.

3-Benzoylaminoxanthone was prepared from 3-aminoxanthone and benzoyl chloride in presence of pyridine. The precipitate obtained on the addition of sufficient ether to the well cooled solution crystallised from alcohol as white shining plates, m. p. 212°. It is soluble in alcohol or acetone, benzene or chloroform. (Found: N, 4.8. $C_{20}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 4.45 per cent).

2-Nitro-7-benzoylaminoxanthone, prepared from 2-nitro-7-aminoxanthone, crystallised from pyridine in light yellow plates not melting below 300°. It is soluble in nitrobenzene or pyridine but insoluble in alcohol or acetone. It gives a very light yellow colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 8.1. $C_{20}H_{12}O_5N_2$ requires N, 7.7 per cent).

Oxaldi-3-xanthonylamide.—To a solution of 3-aminoxanthone (2 mols.) in pyridine oxalyl chloride (1 mol.) was added and the mixture shaken vigorously, when the red colour of the solution gradually changed to light brown. The mixture was heated on a water-bath

for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The resulting product was precipitated by the addition of ether and obtained as a light reddish brown powder. It is only sparingly soluble in alcohol but readily so in pyridine from which it was purified by precipitation with ether. It does not melt below 300° . It could not be reduced to a soluble vat. It gives a light brown colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 6.1. $C_{28}H_{16}O_6N_2$ requires N, 5.8 per cent).

Xanthone-3(1'-azomethine benzene).

To a solution of 3-aminoxanthone (1 mol.) in the minimum quantity of hot alcohol benzaldehyde (1 mol.) was added and the mixture heated gently on a water-bath for about an hour when yellow needles began to separate. The heating was continued for one hour more, when reaction was complete. The solid mass was then collected and washed several times with dilute alcohol, after which it was crystallised from pyridine in fine yellow needles melting at 153° . It is practically insoluble in alcohol or benzene but soluble in nitrobenzene or pyridine. It gives a light yellow colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 4.62. $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 4.68 per cent). The other azomethine compounds are described in Table II.

3-Iodoxanthone.—A well-cooled solution of 3-aminoxanthone (1 g.) in hydrochloric (3 c.c. in 25 c.c. water) was treated with sodium nitrite (0.3 g. in 3 c.c. water). An excess of well-cooled potassium iodide solution was then run into the diazo solution and the mixture left at the room temperature for about 6 hours after which it was heated on the water-bath till the evolution of nitrogen ceased completely. The solution was then triturated with excess of sodium thiosulphate solution, filtered and the iodo compound crystallised from pyridine in beautiful plates having a very light brown (almost white) colour. It melts at 173° . It is soluble in pyridine or nitrobenzene but insoluble in alcohol, acetone and sparingly soluble in carbon disulphide. (Found: I, 40.0. $C_{13}H_7O_2I$ requires I, 39.4 per cent).

2-Iodo-7-nitroxanthone.—2-Amino-7-nitroxanthone (3 g.) was dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (8 c.c.) to which 75 c.c. of water had been added. The whole solution was cooled to 5° and the amino group diazotised by the slow addition of sodium nitrite (0.7 g.

dissolved in 5 c.c. of water cooled to 0°) with constant stirring. After the completion of diazotisation excess of potassium iodide solution was added and the mixture well-stirred. After the addition was complete the mixture was allowed to remain at the room temperature for about two hours after which it was gently heated on the water-bath till the evolution of nitrogen had ceased. The solid mass consisting of a mixture of the iodo compound and free iodine was then triturated with sodium thiosulphate solution in order to remove the excess of iodine. The resulting nitro-iodo-compound crystallised from pyridine in beautiful prismatic plates having a light brown colour, m.p. 235°. It is soluble in pyridine or nitrobenzene but insoluble in alcohol, acetone or benzene. (Found: I, 35.1. $C_{13}H_6O_4NI$ requires I, 34.65 per cent).

TABLE I.

Name of the compound and formula.	Method of preparation.	Does not melt below	Analysis (N).		Remarks.
			Found.	Calc.	
Xanthone-3-1'-azo-2'- naphthol ($C_{23}H_{14}O_3N_2$)	β -Naphthol	300°	8.1	7.6	Deep red microcrystalline powder from acetic acid, soluble in H_2SO_4 (pink). Dyes silk and wool light orange shades from acetic acid and sulphuric acid bath respectively.
Xanthone-3-1'-azo-4'- hydroxy-3'-benzoic acid ($C_{20}H_{12}O_5N_2$).	Salicylic acid	300°	8.4	7.8	Brown powder from acetic acid gives brown colour with conc. H_2SO_4 .
Xanthone-3-1'-azo-2'- hydroxy-3'-naphthoic acid ($C_{24}H_{14}O_5N_2$).	2-Hydroxy- 3-naphthoic acid	300°	6.81	6.8	Deep red powder from acetic acid, gives a reddish violet colouration with H_2SO_4 . Dyes silk and wool in very light pink shades.
Xanthone-3-1'-azo-2'- naphthol-6' : 8'-disulpho- nic acid ($C_{23}H_{14}O_9N_2S_2$).	G-acid	...	5.65	5.3	Deep scarlet-red powder from acetone, soluble in H_2SO_4 (reddish violet). Dyes silk a golden yellow shade.
Xanthone-3-1'-azo-2'- naphthol-3' : 6'-disulpho- nic acid ($C_{23}H_{14}O_9N_2S_2$).	R-acid	...	5.6	5.3	Dark reddish-brown powder from acetone, soluble in H_2SO_4 (pink). Dyes silk and wool a reddish-orange shade.
Xanthone-3-1'-azo- 2 : 4'-dihydroxybenzene ($C_{19}H_{12}O_4N_2$).	Resorcinol	...	8.9	8.4	Dark brown powder from acetic acid, soluble in H_2SO_4 (reddish-brown). Dyes yellow shades on wool and silk.
Xanthone-3-1'-azo-4' dimethylaminobenzene ($C_{21}H_{17}O_2N_3$).	Dimethyl aniline	...	12.5	12.2	Brownish-pink microcrystalline powder from acetone, soluble in H_2SO_4 (pink). Dyes silk and wool a pink shade.

TABLE II.

Name of the compound and formula.	Method of preparation.	M.p.	Analysis (N).		Remarks.
			Found	Calc.	
Xanthone-3 (1'-azomethine-2'-hydroxybenzene). (C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₃ N).	3-Aminoxanthone + Salicylaldehyde	256°	4.8	4.4	Needles from a mixture of nitrobenzene and alcohol.
Xanthone-3 (1'-azomethine-4'-hydroxybenzene). (C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₃ N).	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	264°	4.5	4.4	Prismatic plates from dilute alcohol.
Xanthone-3 (1'-azomethine-3'-hydroxybenzene). (C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₃ N).	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	275°	4.7	4.4	Yellow plates from alcohol.
Xanthone-3 (1'-azomethine-2':4'-dihydroxybenzene). (C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₄ N).	β -Resorcylic aldehyde	does not melt below 290°	4.7	4.2	Deep reddish-brown shining cubes (mixed with prisms) from dilute pyridine.
Xanthone-3 (1'-azomethine-3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxybenzene). (C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₄ N).	Vanillin	241°	4.37	4.06	Deep yellow microcrystalline powder.
Xanthone-3 (1'-azomethine-4'-dimethylaminobenzene). (C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂).	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde	does not melt below 300°	7.9	8.2	Deep yellow powder.
Xanthone 3 (1'-azomethine-4'-chlorobenzene) (C ₂₀ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl).	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	„	Cl, 10.6	11.3	Yellow microcrystalline powder.
Xanthone-3 (1'-azomethine-4'-acetaminobenzene). (C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂).	<i>p</i> -Acetaminobenzaldehyde	„	N, 8.0	8.4	Light yellow powder.
Xanthone-3-cinnamylidene-1'-azomethine (C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N).	Cinnamic aldehyde	„	N, 4.7	4.2	Deep brown plates from pyridine.

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